

A Study on Impact of Technology Adoption and Digital Capability towards the Operational Innovation and Performance of MSME

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Abstract:Purpose – “The purpose of this paper is to study the effect of technology adoption and digital capability on operational innovation and performance of the MSMEs by taking an example from the Regional OEM sector in Chengalpattu districts in Tamil Nadu, India.”

Design/methodology/approach – “This paper develops a conceptual model encompassing Digital Capabilities, Technology Adoption, Operational Innovation and Performance. We use the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to validate this model with 201 MSME employees, supervisors and managers in the OEM Sector.”

Findings – “The empirical results of our data analysis showed that Technology Adoption positively impacted the operation Innovation and Digital Capability has a significant impact on operational Performance. Besides our data indicates that Technology Adoption and Digital Capabilities do not have significant impacts on operational Performance and Innovation, respectively.”

Practical implications – “With that enhanced understanding, OEMs can spotlight their actions on how to improve their Operational Performance and help them to improve the innovative work environment which helps further to perk up their firm’s competitiveness provoked by the Technology adoption mindset in MSMEs.”

Originality/value – “There is a scarcity of research concerning the MSME's development with present advanced technological improvements, this study is believed to be the first that caters to the study on the impact of technology adoption and digital capability on MSMEs for improving operational competitiveness in OEMs with a practical approach.”

Keywords – “OEMs, Manufacturing, Technology Adoption, Digital Capabilities, Operational Innovation, Operational Performance, MSME”

Introduction

When it comes to creating jobs, growing economies, and innovating new products and services, micro, small, and medium-sized businesses (MSMBs) are indispensable. The operational innovation and performance of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are being shaped by their embrace of technology and digital capabilities in today's dynamic and more digitalized business environment. The ability of these enterprises to

harness technological advancements not only enhances their operational efficiency but also propels them towards achieving sustainable growth and competitive advantage in the marketplace.

Technology adoption refers to the process through which businesses incorporate new technological tools, systems, and practices into their operations. For MSMEs, this can range from the implementation of essential digital tools like accounting software and advanced modern technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain. Digital capability, on the other hand, encompasses the skills, knowledge, and resources necessary to effectively utilize these technologies. This includes not only the technical infrastructure but also the human resources trained to manage and leverage digital tools for strategic advantage.

The impact of technology adoption and digital capability on MSMEs encompasses a wide spectrum of transformative effects. From improving Operational processes and enhancing quality to expanding market reach and enabling innovative business models, technology serves as a catalyst for driving operational excellence and fostering innovation within MSMEs. Moreover, digital capabilities empower these enterprises to adapt swiftly to market changes, optimize resource utilization, and leverage data-driven insights for informed decision-making.

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) in India have recently grown into an important part of the country's economy, and their size is one of the control variables used to examine this trend. Concerning coverage in the sector, investment cap, and regulatory matters influencing MSMEs, the MSMED Act was announced in 2006. The updated Classification, Composite Criteria, and Effective Date (July 1, 2020) are detailed below: Plant and machinery investments and yearly turnover. As per the below diagram and enterprise which has investment less than 50 Crore Rupee and Annual turnover less than 250 Crore Rupee can be considered as a MSME in India.

Revised Classification applicable w.e.f 1st July 2020
Composite Criteria: Investment in Plant & Machinery/equipment and Annual Turnover

CLASSIFICATION	MICRO	SMALL	MEDIUM
Manufacturing Enterprises and Enterprises rendering Services	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.1 crore and Annual Turnover : not more than Rs. 5 crore	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.10 crore and Annual Turnover : not more than Rs. 50 crore	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.50 crore and Annual Turnover : not more than Rs. 250 crore

Operational innovation, driven by the strategic application of technology, enables MSMEs to enhance their efficiency, improve product and service offerings, and respond effectively to market demands. On the other hand, these MSME OEM’s performance is increasingly linked to their ability to adapt to technological changes and harness digital solutions for better decision-making, operational agility, and growth.

Despite the evident benefits, the journey towards embracing technology and building digital capabilities poses unique challenges for MSMEs. These challenges include limited financial resources, technological infrastructure constraints, skills gaps among the workforce, and apprehensions regarding cybersecurity and data privacy. Addressing these challenges requires strategic initiatives that encompass policy support, capacity building, and collaborative efforts between stakeholders to create an enabling environment conducive to technology adoption and digital transformation.

This research study seeks to delve deeper into the complex interplay between technology adoption, digital capability, operational innovation, and performance outcomes within MSMEs and specifically in OEMs Sector. By examining empirical evidence and drawing insights from theoretical frameworks, this research aims to uncover the mechanisms through which technology-driven initiatives influence the operational dynamics. Furthermore, it aims to provide actionable recommendations for policymakers, business leaders, and industry stakeholders to enhance the digital readiness and competitiveness of MSMEs in the contemporary business landscape.

2. Literature Review

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) constitute a vital segment of the global economy (Ayyagari, Kunt, & Maksimovic, 2011). In recent years, the advent of digital technologies has revolutionized business operations across industries, presenting unprecedented opportunities for MSMEs to enhance their competitiveness, operational efficiency, and overall performance. Research (Bhatti, Ahmed, & Ferraris, 2022) indicates how the digital capabilities mediate the relationship between Analytics and Innovation and performance of small businesses. Research (Gao & Sarwar, 2022) shows that the Technology Acceptance plays a vital relationship between analytics and Supply chain innovation. Research (Mustafa & Yaakub, 2018) study has presented some evidence on the challenges of innovation and technology and its impact on the company's performance.

Impact of Technology Adoption on MSMEs

The adoption of technology within MSMEs has been widely recognized as a catalyst for driving operational innovation and performance improvements. Digital marketing platforms, cloud computing, and enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems all contribute to increased productivity, decreased costs, and happier customers for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs), according to the research (Cavugil, Nguyen, Hieu, & Seyda, 2017).

When small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) use cloud computing solutions integrated with enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems, they can automate workflows, improve inventory management, and boost CRM capabilities (Marston, Bodnar, Giambona, Harvey, & Graham, 2011). When trying to innovate using technology, organizations often encounter obstacles. Among these obstacles are lack of resources, reluctance to change within organizations, insufficient personnel with the necessary skills, and worries about the privacy and security of sensitive information (Laursen and Salter, 2006). The adoption of strong

cybersecurity measures to protect innovation projects, investment in staff training, and strategic leadership are all necessary to overcome these obstacles (Laursen and Salter, 2006).

Digital Capability and Operational Innovation

An organization's digital capabilities can be defined as its skill in utilizing digital technology to accomplish strategic goals and encourage innovation. MSMEs with strong digital capabilities are better positioned to adapt to technological advancements, capitalize on emerging opportunities, and differentiate themselves in competitive markets (Cheshbrough, Bogers, & Teece, 2019)

Studies highlight that digital capability drives operational innovation within MSMEs by enabling agile decision-making, personalized customer experiences, and the development of innovative products and services (Soto-Acosta, Popa, & Conesa, 2018). The importance of digital capacity in encouraging operational innovation among MSMEs has been highlighted in research conducted by the OECD in 2020. Using data analytics, AI, and the IoT, micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) may improve their understanding of customer behavior, market trends, and operational efficiency.

Gregor *et al.* (2015) found that digital capabilities including cloud computing, real-time data analytics, and agile techniques help businesses be more responsive, flexible, and innovative. This agility is crucial for navigating uncertain environments, mitigating risks, and sustaining long-term growth (Gregor *et al.*, 2015). Organizations encounter barriers to developing and leveraging digital capabilities effectively. These barriers include legacy IT systems, skills gaps, cultural resistance to change, and cybersecurity concerns (Lacity & Willocks, 2018).

Performance Outcomes

The combined impact of technology adoption and digital capability on MSMEs' performance outcomes is multifaceted. Studies indicate that digitally mature MSMEs experience higher profitability, productivity gains, and enhanced market competitiveness compared to their less digitally enabled counterparts (Avgerou, 2017) (Carayannis & Campbell, 2019); (Lacity & Willocks, 2018)). Furthermore, digital transformation contributes to improved customer satisfaction, strengthened supplier relationships, and enhanced overall organizational resilience.

However, the realization of these benefits is contingent upon overcoming various challenges, including financial constraints, skills shortages, cybersecurity threats, and resistance to change (Mansfield-Devine, 2018). Effective strategies for mitigating these challenges involve investing in digital infrastructure, fostering a culture of innovation, and providing training and support to enhance digital literacy among employees (Braun, Clarke, Boulton, & Davey, 2020).

The literatures underscore the transformative potential of technology adoption and digital capability in shaping the operational innovation and performance of MSMEs. By leveraging digital technologies strategically, MSMEs can enhance their operational agility, drive sustainable growth, and contribute to economic resilience. Moving forward, further research is needed to explore emerging technologies such as blockchain and machine learning and their implications for MSMEs in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

3. Hypothesis Development

Hypothesis 1:

Digital Capabilities are Positively related to Operational Performance in Original Equipment manufacturing MSMEs.

Performance and growth are positively correlated with digital competence. While numerous elements contribute to and influence growth trajectory, digital capacity has the potential to enhance opportunity creation and aid survival in competitive environments (Joensuu-Salo & Matalamäki, 2023).

“The study conducted by (Wang, Gu, Ahmad, & Xue, 2022) found that businesses whose leaders were digitally competent had far better financial results. Digital innovation mediates the effect of digital capability on performance within a company, whereas value co-creation mediates the influence of digital capability on performance outside of a firm, according to the results. In the context of digital transformation, this research gives empirical support for organizations establishing digital capabilities and theoretical insight into the mismatch between companies' practice and the potential benefit of digital capability. Thus, based on the above-mentioned qualitative pre-study the hypothesis is developed and its corresponding questionnaire developed.”

Hypothesis 2:

Digital Capabilities are Positively related to Operational Innovation in Original Equipment manufacturing MSMEs.

Digital competence considerably mediates the relationship between digital innovation, performance, and digital transformation, according to the research (Jan & Tian, 2023)

(Radicic & Petković, 2023) Dragana Radicic and Saša Petković's research from 2023 The empirical results show that digitization has different effects on innovative activities for different SMEs. Also, depending on the type of innovation and the degree of digitization, the effects of innovation are small. Internal R&D activities are also investigated as a potential moderator in the study. Involvement in internal R&D appears to mitigate digitalization's innovative effects, according to the results. While digitalization has a positive impact on innovations in products and processes for SMEs that do not participate in internal R&D, it has little effect on SMEs that do.

This relationship between Digital capabilities and Innovation has mixed results in different research, Thus, based on the above-mentioned qualitative pre-study the hypothesis is developed to validate the result.

Hypothesis 3:

Technology Adoption is Positively related to Operational Performance in Original Equipment manufacturing MSMEs.

The results of previous research that used a company's adoption of a single technology to measure its IT expertise were contradictory. (Santos & K., 1995), for instance, failed to discover any substantial correlation between the use of ATMs and key performance indicators like revenue or market share for firms. It is possible for IT to have indirect consequences. We demonstrate, in particular, that organizational learning mediates the relationship between IT competence and business success. This concept builds upon and is consistent with earlier work in this area. The works of (TC & A, 1997) are some examples. Internal and external factors, including the firm's and its trading partners' complementing organizational resources and the competitive and macro environment, determine the amount and characteristics of IT adoption (Melville, Kraemer, & Gurbaxani, 2004).

This relationship between Technology Adoption and Performance has mixed results in different research, Thus, based on the above-mentioned qualitative pre-study the hypothesis is developed to validate the result.

Hypothesis 4:

Technology Adoption is Positively related to Operational Innovation in Original Equipment manufacturing MSMEs.

“This systematic review (Hartley & Benington, 2008) examines how technology adoption in public sector organizations fosters innovation, identifying key factors, challenges, and outcomes based on a comprehensive analysis of existing literature that Technology adoption has positive impact on the Innovation. Little and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) have difficulties, such as slow technological adoption and inefficient use of technology. (Loo, Ramachandran, & Yusof, 2019) found that policymakers can boost the competitiveness if micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) by addressing the challenges

associated with prominent technology use and implementing targeted initiatives that encourage innovation and effective technology adoption.”

In the book chapter (Economic Growth, Vol. 1A, 2005, pp. 949-1003) by Aghion, Philippe, and Howitt, Peter they discussed theoretical framework and shows empirical evidence on how technology adoption and learning process contribute to growth and innovation at the macroeconomic level. Thus, based on the above-mentioned qualitative pre-study the hypothesis is developed and its corresponding questionnaire developed.

Hypothesis 5:

Technology Adoption has a significant positive relationship with Digital Capabilities

“The authors of this comprehensive analysis are (Li, Zhang, & Yang, 2022). Enterprises' economic and environmental performance were impacted by the link between digital technology adoption and digital technology capabilities. Additionally, the impact of digital technology adoption on businesses was amplified by digital strategy. According to the findings of this study (Shen, Zhang, & Liu, 2021), digital transformation performance is more strongly influenced by digital dynamic capability than by the positive correlation between digital technology adoption and performance. There is a positive moderating effect of digital innovation orientation, and of the many forms of digital innovation, efficiency digital innovation is the most important.”

Thus, based on the above-mentioned qualitative pre-study the hypothesis is developed and its corresponding questionnaire developed.

4. Methodology and Design

A conceptual model that includes digital capabilities, technology adoption, operational innovation, and performance is developed in this article. In order to validate this model, we utilized Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with 201 (Hair, black, babin, & anderson, 2009) MSMEs in the OEM Sector.

We used a 4-part survey using a 5-point Likert scale to gather main data from the participants. The 5-point Likert scale provides a straightforward way to interpret responses due to its ordinal nature, where each point represents a degree of agreement or disagreement. This simplicity aids in data analysis and comparison across respondents. (Hair, black, babin, & anderson, 2009). The scale typically includes a neutral midpoint, allowing respondents to indicate a lack of opinion or neutrality on the topic, which can provide more nuanced insights compared to scales without a midpoint (Carifio & Perla, 2007). Responses from a 5-point Likert scale can be analyzed using both parametric and non-parametric statistical methods, depending on the data distribution and research objectives (Norman & Streiner, 2008).

After conducting a pilot study and making necessary revisions to the questionnaire, we used Google Forms to distribute the survey to our target audience online/offline. Our survey of

OEM employees, Supervisors & Managers in the Chengalpattu area of Tamil Nadu, India, yielded 201 valid responses.

The four parts of this survey give more weight to the specifics of each variable (discussed further below). As a data gathering tool, this scale is fine-tuned according to a certain approach. According to (Castrillon & Madakovic, 2010), it also functions as a scale model that may be adjusted to a range of ordinal measurements.

Digital Capabilities – “A Seven item, 5-point Likert scale was used to measure this variable these questions are related to the importance of the Digital capabilities within their organizations.”

Technology Adoption – “A Nine item, 5-point Likert scale was used to measure this variable these questions are related to the importance of the Technology Adoption with respect to their organizations.”

Operational Innovation – “A Seven item, 5-point Likert scale was used to measure this variable these questions are related to the importance of the Innovation within their organizations.”

Operational Performance – “A Seven item, 5-point Likert scale was used to measure this variable these questions are related to the importance of the Performance measure within their organizations.”

From "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," the scale elements measure the level of agreement with the statement:

5. Statistical Analysis and Results

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) based on AMOS is used to evaluate hypotheses in the article. Covariance based structural equation modeling (CB-SEM) is a statistical method for producing SEM estimates (Hair, black, babin, & anderson, 2009). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in CB-SEM uses statistical models to estimate and verify correlations between dependent and independent variables, establishing the constructs' reliability and validity. Latent variables are used to aid in this assessment process (Akter et al., 2011). Detailed information on the variables may be found in [Table 1](#).

Factor Reliability & Validity:

For Testing Factor Reliability, we used Cronbach Alpha to confirm the reliability.

To consider alpha reaching the somewhat arbitrary value of 0.70 as a sufficient measure of reliability or internal consistency of an instrument (Taber, 2017).

For Testing Factor Validity, we used KMO and Barlett Test

The value of KMO should be above 0.6 (Hadia, Waal, & Meer, 2016).

For Bartlett's test the significant value less than 0.05 indicates that these data are acceptable for further analysis (Pallant, 2013)

Demographics data analysis of the respondents:

Demographic and Job Profile of the Respondents for the Primary Data (Sample Size: 201) available in [Table 9](#)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model fit:

“We employ goodness-of-fit indices like the GFI and CMIN Chi-Square to assess the model's accuracy. The adjusted goodness of fit (AGFI) is a parsimonious measure of model fit, while the CFI comparative fit index reflects model fit in this case (Keramati et al., 2010). The other metrics of fit, including TLI, AGFI, GFI, and chi-square divided by degree of freedom (CMIN/DF), were also determined to be 1.107, 0.99, 0.857, and 0.877, respectively. The model's CFI value is 0.991 and the RMSEA root mean square error of approximation value is 0.059, as reported in Table 2. Additionally, our model's p-value was found to be 0.069 in the analysis.” These readings are all within the acceptable range (Table 3). (Miljko, 2020)

“Degree of Freedom and Result of the model from AMOS:

Computation of degrees of freedom (Default model)

Number of distinct sample moments: 465

Number of distinct parameters to be estimated: 65

Degrees of freedom (465 - 65): 400

Result (Default model):

Minimum was achieved.

Chi-square = 442.767”

Degrees of freedom = 400 According to (Jorgeskog & Surbom, 1996), an adequate fit is indicated by a p-value of ≥ 0.05 . In this case, a p-value of 0.69 seems to be acceptable.

Probability level = .069

According to (Jorgeskog & Surbom, 1996), an adequate fit is indicated by a p-value of ≥ 0.05 . In this case, a p-value of 0.69 seems to be acceptable.

Below is the Path diagram of the model: ([Table 4](#))

6. Hypothesis Testing

In AMOS, the SEM method was employed to examine the direct and indirect impacts. Table 5 below summarizes the study's findings.

H1: From the below table we could see the Hypothesis P-Value is significant.

“The Digital Capabilities has a significant positive impact on the Operational Performance. The result is like the other results that we have seen in the Literatures.”

H2: From the below table we could see the Hypothesis is not significant.

“The Digital Capabilities does not have a significant impact on the Operational Innovation. The result is like the other results that we have seen in the Literatures.”

H3: From the below table we could see the Hypothesis is not significant.

“The Technology Adoption does not have a significant impact on the Operational Performance. The result is like the other results that we have seen in the Literatures.”

H4: From the below table we could see the Hypothesis P-Value is significant.

“The Technology Adoption has a significant positive impact on the Operational Performance. The result is matching the other results that we have seen in the Literatures.”

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Innovation	<---	TechAdop	1.144	.486	2.355	.019
Innovation	<---	DigitalCap	-.189	.443	-.428	.669
Performance	<---	TechAdop	-1.579	2.651	-.595	.552
Performance	<---	DigitalCap	2.363	.948	2.492	.043

H5: We have a significant Correlation between the two Latent Variable Digital Capabilities and Technology Adoption as show in the Table 6 , We could see the Covariance P-Value is significant for the Latent Variables Digital Capabilities and Technology Adoption

The Total Direct, Indirect effect of the Latent Variables are given in Table 7

Overall Hypothesis Summary

Digital Capabilities → Operational Performance → Significant

Digital Capabilities → Operational Innovation → Not Significant

Technology Adoption → Operational Performance → Not Significant

Technology Adoption → Operational Innovation → Significant

Digital Capabilities $\leftrightarrow$ Technology Adoption $\rightarrow$ Significant

7. Conclusion and Discussion

The Study analyses the impact of technology adoption and digital capabilities towards the operational innovation and Operational performances of the OEMs. As far as the specified research about that specific area is concerned, this is a major step forward. This article further validates some of the relationship confirms the similarities between the results of this regional result with some of the global research. According to (Ayyagari, Kunt, & Maksimovic, 2011), micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) play a crucial role in the global economy. In recent years, the advent of digital technologies has revolutionized business operations across industries, presenting unprecedented opportunities for MSMEs to enhance their competitiveness, operational efficiency, and overall performance.

This research provides valuable inputs on identifying the complex relationships of the Latent Variable to draw actionable insights that can be used by the MSMEs. To test the hypothesis, this study employed structural equation modeling (SEM) with AMOS, a statistical method for analyzing complex interactions between observable and latent variables. Its evaluation and development of theoretical models find widespread use in many disciplines, including the social sciences, psychology, economics, and others. We used 5-point Likert scale to collect the data which is a straightforward approach as it gives us the ordinal data.

The practical implication of this research is that the study helps OEMs to keep up with the rapidly changing technology advancements in the sector that need improvements in their performance and innovation capabilities. our study claims that Digital capabilities helps improve performance and not have a significant relationship with innovation as supported by other studies. On the other hand, Technology Adoption environment in the company helps in innovation but does not have significant relationship with performance as supported by other studies. The managers can practically utilize these insights to exactly identify where to invest time and effort for the corresponding improvements either in performance or innovation. The correlation between Digital Capabilities and Technology Adoption proves that both goes hand in hand and critical for the performance and Innovation of any enterprise.

Technology adoption offers practical benefits for MSMEs by accelerating research and development. It provides the necessary tools to create new products or enhance existing ones, thereby driving growth and market expansion. Digital capabilities enable effective data gathering and analysis, leading to more informed decision-making. Real-time data access aids in making strategic adjustments and predicting future trends. Advanced analytics tools facilitate more accurate performance monitoring and evaluation, leading to better strategic planning and operational adjustments.

The Theoretical implication of this research is that the study can extend the Technology Acceptance Model by exploring how various technologies perceived usefulness and ease of use influence MSME's adoption decisions. It can provide insights into how MSMEs evaluate the benefits and usability of technological tools before integrating them into their operations.

The research can extend the Dynamic Capabilities Theory by illustrating how technology adoption enhances an MSME's ability to adapt to market volatility and innovate. It offers a theoretical lens to understand how digital capabilities enable MSMEs to reconfigure their operational processes and respond to evolving industry demands. Understanding the impact of technology adoption on operational innovation can refine DOI theory by highlighting how MSME's level of innovativeness affects their technology adoption decisions and subsequent performance outcomes.

We learned from this article that operational innovation and digital capabilities go hand in hand. Similarly, technology adoption goes hand in hand with operational performance. On the other hand, Technology adoption and digital capabilities does not have a significant relation with Operational Performance and Operational Innovation, respectively. Both the insights we drew through our research gets validated with the literatures that has been discussed before.

The Limitation of this research is that it only covers the Chengalpattu district in the Indian state of Tamil Nadu. It is possible that the results of this study do not apply nationwide. Other regions in India may have a unique perspective based on their macro and micro economic conditions, and thus, future studies can be conducted in a different area. The present study investigated the relationship directly. The mediation effect with data analytics capabilities can be considered in future research. Technology's fast-paced evolution can impact the research findings' relevance and accuracy. Technologies and digital tools that are effective today might become obsolete or replaced by more advanced solutions in a short period, affecting the long-term applicability of the results. As new technologies emerge, MSMEs' adoption practices and digital capabilities might change, potentially impacting the relevance of the research findings over time.

8. Abbreviation

“DC – Digital Capabilities”

“TA – Technology Adoption”

“OI – Operational Innovation”

“OP – Operational Performance”

“SEM – Structural Equation Modelling”

“CB-SEM – Covariance Based Structural Equation Modelling”

“MSME – Micro Small and Medium Enterprises”

“OEM – Original Equipment Manufacturers”

“CMIN – Chi Square”

“DF – Degree of Freedom”

“R & D – Research and Development”

“SME – Small and Medium Enterprises”

“CFA – Confirmatory Factor Analysis”

“GFI – Goodness of Fit Index”

“RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation”

“CFI – Comparative fit index”

“DOI-Diffusion of Innovation”

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Attachments

Table 1:

Number of variables in your model:	66
Number of observed variables:	30
Number of unobserved variables:	36
Number of exogenous variables:	34
Number of endogenous variables:	32

Construct	Mean	Std. Deviation
Digital Capabilities	3.023	1.29
Technology Adoption	2.988	1.274
Operational Performance	3.01	1.262
Operational Innovation	3.022	1.267

Dimension	Cronbach Alpha Value	Items
Digital Capabilities	0.911818538	7
Technology Adoption	0.933170713	9
Operational Innovation	0.910392365	7
Operational Performance	0.910571284	7
Total	0.9841	30

Dimension	KMO	Bartlett's test of Sphericity
Data Analytics Capabilities	0.966	.000
Digital Capabilities	0.935	.000
Technology Adoption	0.957	.000
Operational Innovation	0.928	.000
Operational Performance	0.934	.000
Total	0.982	.000

RMSEA

Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default model	.023	.000	.035	1.000
Independence model	.232	.227	.238	.000

Model Fit Summary

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	65	442.767	400	.069	1.107
Saturated model	465	.000	0		
Independence model	30	5135.540	435	.000	11.806

RMR, GFI

Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI
Default model	.044	.877	.857	.755
Saturated model	.000	1.000		
Independence model	.935	.088	.026	.083

Baseline Comparisons

Model	NFI Delta1	RFI rho1	IFI Delta2	TLI rho2	CFI
Default model	.914	.906	.991	.990	.991
Saturated model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Independence model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Parsimony-Adjusted Measures

Model	PRATIO	PNFI	PCFI
Default model	.920	.840	.911
Saturated model	.000	.000	.000
Independence model	1.000	.000	.000

Table 3:

Acronym	Explication	Accepted fit	Resulting
---------	-------------	--------------	-----------

			fit
CMIN/DF	Chi-square divided by degrees of freedom	<3 it indicates an acceptable fit ≤ 5 it indicates a reasonable fit	1.107
RMSEA	Root mean square error of approximation	≤ 0,05 are considered excellent ≤ 0,08 are considered acceptable	0.023
GFI	Goodness of fit Index	≥ 0,80 indicates a acceptable fit ≥ 0,90 indicates a reasonable fit ≥ 0,95 is considered an excellent fit	0.877
CFI	Comparative fit index	≥ 0,90 indicates a acceptable fit ≥ 0,95 is considered an excellent fit	0.991
TLI	Tucker-Lewis index	≥ 0,90 indicates a reasonable fit ≥ 0,95 is considered an excellent fit	0.99

Table 4 :

Table 5:

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Innovation	<--- TechAdop	1.144	.486	2.355	.019

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Innovation	<---	DigitalCap	-.189	.443	-.428	.669
Performance	<---	TechAdop	-1.579	2.651	-.595	.552
Performance	<---	DigitalCap	2.363	.948	2.492	.043

Table 6:

Covariances: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TechAdop	<-->	DigitalCap	1.070	.137	7.796	***	par_30

Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
TechAdop	<-->	DigitalCap	.994

Table 7

Total Effect:

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Innovation	<---	TechAdop	1.144	.486	2.355	.019	par_15
Innovation	<---	DigitalCap	-.189	.443	-.428	.669	par_22
Performance	<---	TechAdop	-1.579	2.651	-.595	.552	par_29
Performance	<---	DigitalCap	2.363	.948	2.492	.043	par_31
TA9	<---	TechAdop	1.000				
TA8	<---	TechAdop	1.072	.084	12.748	***	par_1
TA7	<---	TechAdop	1.009	.083	12.187	***	par_2
TA6	<---	TechAdop	.949	.080	11.918	***	par_3
TA5	<---	TechAdop	.995	.083	12.033	***	par_4
TA4	<---	TechAdop	.969	.081	12.013	***	par_5
TA3	<---	TechAdop	1.000	.081	12.272	***	par_6
TA2	<---	TechAdop	.978	.081	12.006	***	par_7
TA1	<---	TechAdop	.931	.079	11.825	***	par_8
OI1	<---	Innovation	1.000				
OI3	<---	Innovation	1.072	.093	11.537	***	par_9
OI4	<---	Innovation	1.128	.091	12.399	***	par_10
OI5	<---	Innovation	1.008	.088	11.446	***	par_11

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
OI6	<---	Innovation	.967	.086	11.264	***	par_12
OI7	<---	Innovation	1.004	.088	11.404	***	par_13
OI8	<---	Innovation	1.014	.087	11.717	***	par_14
DC1	<---	DigitalCap	1.000				
DC2	<---	DigitalCap	.851	.072	11.873	***	par_16
DC3	<---	DigitalCap	.931	.074	12.566	***	par_17
DC4	<---	DigitalCap	.895	.071	12.647	***	par_18
DC5	<---	DigitalCap	.964	.076	12.639	***	par_19
DC6	<---	DigitalCap	.916	.073	12.477	***	par_20
DC7	<---	DigitalCap	.932	.074	12.516	***	par_21
OP8	<---	Performance	1.000				
OP7	<---	Performance	1.040	.085	12.206	***	par_23
OP6	<---	Performance	1.002	.086	11.651	***	par_24
OP5	<---	Performance	1.101	.090	12.236	***	par_25
OP4	<---	Performance	.973	.085	11.484	***	par_26
OP3	<---	Performance	.978	.083	11.838	***	par_27
OP2	<---	Performance	1.101	.092	12.028	***	par_28

Standardized Total Effect:

	DigitalCap	TechAdop	Performance	Innovation
Performance	2.671	-1.669	.000	.000
Innovation	-.215	1.214	.000	.000
OP2	2.076	-1.298	.777	.000
OP3	2.050	-1.281	.767	.000
OP4	1.999	-1.249	.748	.000
OP5	2.105	-1.316	.788	.000
OP6	2.023	-1.264	.757	.000
OP7	2.101	-1.313	.787	.000
OP8	2.055	-1.284	.769	.000
DC7	.770	.000	.000	.000
DC6	.768	.000	.000	.000
DC5	.776	.000	.000	.000
DC4	.776	.000	.000	.000
DC3	.772	.000	.000	.000
DC2	.740	.000	.000	.000
DC1	.799	.000	.000	.000
OI8	-.167	.945	.000	.778

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
OI7	-.163	.923	.000	.760
OI6	-.162	.913	.000	.752
OI5	-.164	.926	.000	.763
OI4	-.175	.992	.000	.817
OI3	-.165	.932	.000	.768
OI1	-.162	.914	.000	.753
TA1	.000	.764	.000	.000
TA2	.000	.774	.000	.000
TA3	.000	.788	.000	.000
TA4	.000	.774	.000	.000
TA5	.000	.775	.000	.000
TA6	.000	.769	.000	.000
TA7	.000	.783	.000	.000
TA8	.000	.812	.000	.000
TA9	.000	.771	.000	.000

Direct Effect:

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
Performance	2.363	-1.579	.000	.000
Innovation	-.189	1.144	.000	.000
OP2	.000	.000	1.101	.000
OP3	.000	.000	.978	.000
OP4	.000	.000	.973	.000
OP5	.000	.000	1.101	.000
OP6	.000	.000	1.002	.000
OP7	.000	.000	1.040	.000
OP8	.000	.000	1.000	.000
DC7	.932	.000	.000	.000
DC6	.916	.000	.000	.000
DC5	.964	.000	.000	.000
DC4	.895	.000	.000	.000
DC3	.931	.000	.000	.000
DC2	.851	.000	.000	.000
DC1	1.000	.000	.000	.000

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
OI8	.000	.000	.000	1.014
OI7	.000	.000	.000	1.004
OI6	.000	.000	.000	.967
OI5	.000	.000	.000	1.008
OI4	.000	.000	.000	1.128
OI3	.000	.000	.000	1.072
OI1	.000	.000	.000	1.000
TA1	.000	.931	.000	.000
TA2	.000	.978	.000	.000
TA3	.000	1.000	.000	.000
TA4	.000	.969	.000	.000
TA5	.000	.995	.000	.000
TA6	.000	.949	.000	.000
TA7	.000	1.009	.000	.000
TA8	.000	1.072	.000	.000
TA9	.000	1.000	.000	.000

Standardized Direct Effect:

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
Performance	2.671	-1.669	.000	.000
Innovation	-.215	1.214	.000	.000
OP2	.000	.000	.777	.000
OP3	.000	.000	.767	.000
OP4	.000	.000	.748	.000
OP5	.000	.000	.788	.000
OP6	.000	.000	.757	.000
OP7	.000	.000	.787	.000
OP8	.000	.000	.769	.000
DC7	.770	.000	.000	.000
DC6	.768	.000	.000	.000
DC5	.776	.000	.000	.000
DC4	.776	.000	.000	.000
DC3	.772	.000	.000	.000
DC2	.740	.000	.000	.000

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
DC1	.799	.000	.000	.000
OI8	.000	.000	.000	.778
OI7	.000	.000	.000	.760
OI6	.000	.000	.000	.752
OI5	.000	.000	.000	.763
OI4	.000	.000	.000	.817
OI3	.000	.000	.000	.768
OI1	.000	.000	.000	.753
TA1	.000	.764	.000	.000
TA2	.000	.774	.000	.000
TA3	.000	.788	.000	.000
TA4	.000	.774	.000	.000
TA5	.000	.775	.000	.000
TA6	.000	.769	.000	.000
TA7	.000	.783	.000	.000
TA8	.000	.812	.000	.000
TA9	.000	.771	.000	.000

Indirect Effect:

	DigitalCap TechAdop Performance Innovation			
Performance	.000	.000	.000	.000
Innovation	.000	.000	.000	.000
OP2	2.601	-1.738	.000	.000
OP3	2.310	-1.544	.000	.000
OP4	2.299	-1.536	.000	.000
OP5	2.600	-1.737	.000	.000
OP6	2.368	-1.582	.000	.000
OP7	2.457	-1.642	.000	.000
OP8	2.363	-1.579	.000	.000
DC7	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC6	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC5	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC4	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC3	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC2	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC1	.000	.000	.000	.000
OI8	-.192	1.160	.000	.000
OI7	-.190	1.148	.000	.000
OI6	-.183	1.107	.000	.000
OI5	-.191	1.154	.000	.000
OI4	-.214	1.291	.000	.000

	DigitalCap	TechAdop	Performance	Innovation
OI3	-.203	1.226	.000	.000
OI1	-.189	1.144	.000	.000
TA1	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA2	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA3	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA4	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA5	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA6	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA7	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA8	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA9	.000	.000	.000	.000

Standardized Indirect Effect

	DigitalCap	TechAdop	Performance	Innovation
Performance	.000	.000	.000	.000
Innovation	.000	.000	.000	.000
OP2	2.076	-1.298	.000	.000
OP3	2.050	-1.281	.000	.000
OP4	1.999	-1.249	.000	.000
OP5	2.105	-1.316	.000	.000
OP6	2.023	-1.264	.000	.000
OP7	2.101	-1.313	.000	.000
OP8	2.055	-1.284	.000	.000
DC7	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC6	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC5	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC4	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC3	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC2	.000	.000	.000	.000
DC1	.000	.000	.000	.000
OI8	-.167	.945	.000	.000
OI7	-.163	.923	.000	.000
OI6	-.162	.913	.000	.000
OI5	-.164	.926	.000	.000
OI4	-.175	.992	.000	.000
OI3	-.165	.932	.000	.000
OI1	-.162	.914	.000	.000
TA1	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA2	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA3	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA4	.000	.000	.000	.000

	DigitalCap	TechAdop	Performance	Innovation
TA5	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA6	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA7	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA8	.000	.000	.000	.000
TA9	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 8

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Innovation	<---	TechAdop	1.144	.486	2.355	.019	par_15
Innovation	<---	DigitalCap	-.189	.443	-.428	.669	par_22
Performance	<---	TechAdop	-1.579	2.651	-.595	.552	par_29
Performance	<---	DigitalCap	2.363	.948	2.492	.043	par_31
TA9	<---	TechAdop	1.000				
TA8	<---	TechAdop	1.072	.084	12.748	***	par_1
TA7	<---	TechAdop	1.009	.083	12.187	***	par_2
TA6	<---	TechAdop	.949	.080	11.918	***	par_3
TA5	<---	TechAdop	.995	.083	12.033	***	par_4
TA4	<---	TechAdop	.969	.081	12.013	***	par_5
TA3	<---	TechAdop	1.000	.081	12.272	***	par_6
TA2	<---	TechAdop	.978	.081	12.006	***	par_7
TA1	<---	TechAdop	.931	.079	11.825	***	par_8
OI1	<---	Innovation	1.000				
OI3	<---	Innovation	1.072	.093	11.537	***	par_9
OI4	<---	Innovation	1.128	.091	12.399	***	par_10
OI5	<---	Innovation	1.008	.088	11.446	***	par_11
OI6	<---	Innovation	.967	.086	11.264	***	par_12
OI7	<---	Innovation	1.004	.088	11.404	***	par_13
OI8	<---	Innovation	1.014	.087	11.717	***	par_14
DC1	<---	DigitalCap	1.000				
DC2	<---	DigitalCap	.851	.072	11.873	***	par_16
DC3	<---	DigitalCap	.931	.074	12.566	***	par_17
DC4	<---	DigitalCap	.895	.071	12.647	***	par_18
DC5	<---	DigitalCap	.964	.076	12.639	***	par_19
DC6	<---	DigitalCap	.916	.073	12.477	***	par_20
DC7	<---	DigitalCap	.932	.074	12.516	***	par_21
OP8	<---	Performance	1.000				
OP7	<---	Performance	1.040	.085	12.206	***	par_23
OP6	<---	Performance	1.002	.086	11.651	***	par_24
OP5	<---	Performance	1.101	.090	12.236	***	par_25
OP4	<---	Performance	.973	.085	11.484	***	par_26
OP3	<---	Performance	.978	.083	11.838	***	par_27

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
OP2	<--- Performance	1.101	.092	12.028	***	par_28

Table 9 :

Variables	Options	Frequencies	(% rounded off to whole number)
Age in Years	20-30 Years	Open ended Questions	18%
	31-40 Years		62%
	>40 Years		20%
Association with the OEM (Years)	0-2 Years	Open ended Questions	10%
	3-6 Years		40%
	>6 Years		50%
Gender	Male	201 0	100%
	Female		
Education	Undergraduate	145 56	72%
	Postgraduate & Higher		28%

Type of Research	Descriptive and Exploratory research
Research Approach	Combination of Qualitative and Quantitative Approach
Sampling and Population of research	Employees, Supervisors & Managers from Manufacturing OEMs in Chengalpattu District of Tamilnadu State in India
Sample Size	201 Employees, Supervisors & Managers from manufacturing OEMs
Study Location	Chengalpattu District of Tamilnadu
Primary Data Collection	Questionnaire (Majority) and In-Person Interview
Secondary Data Source	Books, Research Articles, Reports, Journals and other online source
Data Collection Period	December 2023 to February 2024
Data Collection Software	Google Forms
Data Analysis Software's	MS Excel 2016, SPSS, SPSS AMOS